

STUDENTS OF PEDAGOGICAL UNIVERSITIES COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCES FORMATION METHODOLOGY

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Annotation: In this article, the formation of a pedagogue who can fully meet the demands of the reforms implemented in society today, is resistant to the competition in the production sector, can adapt to sudden changes, and also works effectively at the level of the requirements for the qualifications of specialists in the labor market. theoretical foundations are explained.

Key words: professional competence, competence, theory, pedagogy, methodology, school, higher education, modern society, personality, psychology,

Modern society requires the education system to educate highly qualified, aspiring, competitive, enterprising, spiritually and physically healthy individuals. In the action strategy for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021, "Education of a highly educated and intellectually developed generation, who is a competent pedagogue in higher education institutions?" Questions arise, such as how the process of its formation takes place. From this point of view, it is important to define the meaning of the concepts of "competency" and "competence".

Recently, the concept of "competence" is widely used in the psychological and pedagogical literature and in the scientific works of many pedagogic scientists. Formation of the professional competence of the primary teacher has a special place among the complex problems in the training of pedagogues.

The concept of "competency" is an ever-growing classification of a person, and it is the ability to solve problems in real life situations, the ability to mobilize one's knowledge, educational and life experiences, values and interests.

The term "competency" entered the field of education as a result of the scientific research of psychologists. This concept shows the need for theoretical knowledge about how to behave in unconventional or unexpected situations, how to act in uncertain situations, how to act in ever-evolving and complex processes when using conflicting information. Competence requires constantly enriching one's knowledge, learning new information, feeling the demand of this day and age, the skill of finding new knowledge, processing it and applying it in one's practical work.

A competent specialist knows how to use the methods and methods that are suitable for this situation, he can selectively use the methods that are suitable for the current situation, he rejects the ones that are not appropriate, will have skills such as looking with a critical eye.

Competent approach of pedagogues is not a completely new phenomenon, but its tributaries exist in continuously developing educational processes, and they are formed step by step. In particular, the problem of adapting to pedagogical activity is becoming more evident. Along

with practical, psychological, methodical, research types, future teachers are enriched by forming the professional competence of the teacher.

It is necessary to include diagnostic, communicative, management and projective training groups in the essential characteristics of professional competence diagnosis and formation. The pedagogue's cognitive activity is largely determined by the complexity, dynamics, non-standardity of the things being studied, the influence of the boundaries that distinguish social phenomena, their search, uncertainty, which implies observation, the ability to model the inner world of the interlocutor.

In this case, the characteristics of self-regulation are characterized by the need to constantly improve one's knowledge and skills, and the ability to constantly coordinate one's actions towards other people. We can define the concept of "teacher's professional competence" as follows:

The professional competence of the teacher is one of the important aspects of the professional competence in the activities of the pedagogue, and it expresses all the needs, abilities, skills, knowledge and interests of the pedagogue related to the implementation of the profession and professional activity.

Professionalism and competence are similar terms, but they have different meanings. Professionalism means not only certain knowledge, but also attitude to work, specific characteristics of work. The developed competences are immediately felt, because the professional pedagogue strives to develop his skills, produces workable values, and these usually correspond to the standard of the work process.

Competence has a somewhat complicated meaning, because it specifies not only the existence of knowledge, but also the ability to apply it. Competence can only be determined during extensive evaluation and observation. Concepts of professionalism and competence have a general character. It should be noted that people who fully meet the requirements and standards do not always become true professionals, because some of them do not know how to apply their knowledge in practice, so such pedagogical activity remains ineffective.

Workers with a high level of personal pedagogical competence are less prone to burnout and are able to work under time pressure. Each type of competence includes a set of skills, knowledge and skills. In pedagogues, they appear at different levels. It is possible to determine how this or other competencies have been developed by paying attention to the indicators of his behavior in the performance of service duties.

How is competence formed? The main thing for the formation of the teacher's competence is special professional education. In the future, the knowledge and skills acquired in practice will complement the level of initial competence. D. L. Thompson. D. Pristins claim that professional competence is the sum of knowledge and all ethical rules needed at work. I.V. Grishina assesses professional competence as the extent to which a person has mastered his professional activity and defines it as follows:

According to A.K. Markova, the scientist who searched for the basics of the professional competence of the teacher's work, the teacher's work becomes competent when the teacher performs his activities at a sufficiently high level and teaches and educates students at a high level. Along with these bases, the teacher's professional competence is studied in four parts:

1. Special or functional professional competence is the ability to carry out activities at a high professional level. Special professional competence consists not only of special knowledge, but also of the implementation of this knowledge.

2. Social competence is knowing how to carry out additional activities, knowing how to do it in cooperation.

3. Personal competence - knowing the ways of self-development and self-presentation (the specialist can plan his activities, make independent decisions, plan, work with information and on himself)

4. Individual competence is knowing how to manage oneself, preparing for professional development and creating professional innovations.

At the same time, the teacher's knowledge should be enriched with innovations. psychological and pedagogical qualities should be at a high level.

In the multi-level educational system, it is impossible to allow the educational process to be carried out within the framework of standards and programs according to outdated methods. It is necessary to strengthen comprehensive structural reforms in the educational system by the pedagogues of the Republic by mastering advanced pedagogical technologies and applying them to the educational process. As mentioned earlier, for this, it is necessary to train our pedagogues in technological approaches to the educational process. This, in addition to the use of pedagogical technologies, enriches it with the culture, traditions and experience of Uzbekistan.

Certain qualities of a person are formed through a set of actual educational activities. It is necessary for these works to be clearly multifaceted, and at the same time to carry out mental, physical, moral, aesthetic and labor education based on its integrity. A comprehensive educational approach requires a systematic attitude and management of the educator. Management can be successful only when taking into account the external and internal factors involved in the education process and their interaction. Therefore, it is necessary to have an idea about the factors.

In the process of educational work, it is important to teach students to think creatively, to adapt to changing situations, to organize their activities on the basis of free competition, and to use information technologies, electronic textbooks, versions and multimedia in practical training. It is necessary to turn students into their internal need for independent free thinking, upbringing, analysis of educational activities, and the achievement of clearly defining plans for acquiring professional skills and computer literacy in the future.

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